

Synthetic hydrous titanium(IV) oxide (HTO) : Adsorptive removal of lead(II) from the contaminated industrial waste water^ψ

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The present study reports a systematic adsorption of lead(II) onto hydrated titanium(IV) oxide (HTO) from the aqueous solutions at 30 (±3)°C by batch and column methods. The particle size of HTO used is in the range 140 to 290 μm. Effect of pH, contact time for kinetics, adsorption isotherm etc. and breakthrough with influent lead(II) concentration, flow rate and bed depth variations studies are reported by batch and column methods, respectively. The optimum pH range found for maximum lead(II) sorption is 5.0 to 6.0. The adsorption data fit the tested adsorption isotherms in the following order : Langmuir > Freundlich > Temkin. Three kinetic models viz. the power function, the simple Elovich and the pseudo second-order are tested for fitting the experimental equilibrium data. Both the power function and the simple Elovich equations are found to fit best at lower adsorbate concentrations. No remarkable influence was found on adsorption of lead(II) by the cations and anions tested. 0.5 M HNO₃ was found to be an efficient agent, which could desorb 90.0 to 92.0% of the adsorbed lead(II) from the saturated adsorbent. Column adsorption method has been applied to contaminated waste water sample of Exide India Limited (EIL) at Shyamnagar, North 24-Pargans, W.B., India.

Disposal of lead(II) contaminated industrial waste water is a serious problem throughout the globe. Many industries such as storage battery, printing and pigment, zinc mine and smelters are in a great problem to discharge their wastewaters. Synthetic hydrous titanium(IV) oxide (HTO) is well known for its ion exchange and surface adsorption properties¹. It is a synthetic crystalline compound with surface hydroxyl groups for metal ion uptake by ion exchange and surface oxo groups for van der Waals type of coulombic sorption. Moreover, it is a non-toxic and highly insoluble solid even at low pH values.

We report herein a systematic study on the ability of HTO to uptake lead(II) from the aqueous solution. The variable parameters viz. the effect of pH, contact time for adsorption kinetics, isotherms, influence of some other ions and desorption have been reported from batch equilibration data. In addition, the breakthrough studies with varying influent lead(II), downflow rate and bed depth at optimum pH, and at temperature 30 (±3)°C have been reported by column method. Finally, removal and recovery of lead(II) from a contaminated industrial waste effluent has been reported using a fixed bed HTO column.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH : With initial loading of 7.22, 12.02 and 24.04 μmol lead(II)/g of adsorbent showed that the adsorption amount of the adsorbate species was increased with increasing initial pH up to 5.0 of the experimental system, and it became thereafter nearly same. Thus, the optimum initial pH range for maximum lead(II) sorption onto HTO is 5.0 to 6.0. The striking feature of our experimental observation was that the decrease in final pH up to the initial pH of 3.0 was negligible, while that for initial pH 4.0, and above was notable. The decrease in final pH than the initial (pH ≥ 4.0) indicates that the adsorption of lead(II) onto the adsorbent takes place by exchange of hydrogen ion of hydroxyl part of HTO. At pH < 4.0, the adsorption of lead(II) from the solution is thought to take place via van der Waals type of electrostatic interaction. Thus the probable mechanism on lead(II) sorption at optimum pH range could be depicted as below :

^ψA part of this work was presented in the Annual Convention of Chemists, 2003 at Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (U.P.), India.

At pH > 6.5, it was found that lead(II) appeared as hydroxide precipitate when the initial loading was 24.04 μmol/g. Thus, the working initial pH range chosen for the rest part of the experiments was 5.0 to 6.0.

Determination of contact time for lead(II) adsorption onto HTO at an initial pH of 5.0 with loading 7.22, 12.02, and 24.04 μmol lead(II)/g of adsorbent showed that the time required for reaching equilibrium and maximum uptake was independent on initial concentration of adsorbate. Initial rapid uptake is thought to be due to the rapid mass transfer effect onto the exchangeable surface active sites of the adsorbent. Rest ~50% uptake took place until equilibrium reached. The later slow adsorption is probably due to (i) intra particle transport, and (ii) the slow pore-diffusion process of adsorbate ion from solution.

Adsorption capacity : Lead(II) adsorption capacity was determined by batch method. This value depends upon the initial loading of any sorbate species per unit weight of the adsorbent. However, when loading of adsorbate species would be much greater than the available active sites of the adsorbent added, then adsorption capacity obtained should be thought to be highest. Thus, loading 0.24 mmol lead(II)/g of adsorbent at an initial pH 5.0 gave an adsorption capacity of 0.206 (±0.009) mmol/g. This is nearly 80% of the initial loading of lead(II) in solution indicating a good prospect on use of HTO as an adsorbent in the field for contaminated waste effluent treatment.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on lead(II) adsorption onto HTO at temperature 30 (±3)°C.

Adsorption kinetics : The equilibrium data showed in Fig. 2 have been used for kinetics evaluation. Here, three adsorption kinetic model (Power function, Simple Elovich and pseudo-second order) equations were used to fit the kinetic data by linear regressions². Model equations for

Fig. 2. The time of equilibration on lead(II) adsorption onto HTO at pH 5 and at temperature 30 (±3)°C.

adsorption kinetic experiments at 30 (±3)°C for lead(II) and estimated parameters with regression coefficient (R^2) and standard square error (SE)) are shown in Table I. Based on R^2 and SE, the kinetics of lead(II) adsorption onto HTO could be described well by both Power function and Simple Elovich equations up to the initial sorbate concentration of 24.05 μM/L ($R^2 > 0.95$), while for 48.10 μM/L solution, pseudo-second order equation fits well ($R^2 > 0.95$).

Table I. Estimated kinetic model parameters for lead(II) adsorption by CHTO

Equations	Parameters	Initial concentration of lead(II) solution (μ mol/L)		
		14.43	24.05	48.10
Power function ^a equation	a	1.9498	3.1623	6.3096
	b	0.3300	0.36	0.38
	$\log q = \log a + b \log t$	R^2	0.9819	0.9893
	SE	0.0189	0.0135	0.0495
Simple Elovich equation	a	1.0	1.8	9.8
	b	3.3333	5.769	8.077
	$q = a + 2.303 b \log t$	R^2	0.9627	0.9847
	SE	0.3267	0.3288	1.6497
Pseudo-second order equation	a	0.7018	0.3773	0.2174
	b	0.144	0.088	0.040
	$1/q = a/t + b$	R^2	0.8671	0.9395
	SE	0.0236	0.0087	0.0027

Adsorption isotherm : Three linear forms of adsorption isotherm eqs. (1 to 3) were used for fitting the experimental data.

$$\text{Langmuir equation : } 1/q = 1/(\theta \cdot b \cdot C) + 1/\theta \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Freundlich equation : } \log q = \log K + 1/n \log C \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Temkin equation : } q = a + 2.303 b \log C \quad (3)$$

where q is the amount of adsorbed lead(II) (μmol/g), and C

capacities are 382.40 (± 10.25), 444.93 (± 9.95) and 649.35 (± 11.15) μmol respectively. The breakthrough and column capacities at a low flow rate are higher than high flow rate, which agrees well to the theoretical idea. The leakage point volume of treated water decreased proportionately with varying influent load. This is agrees to the fact that the adsorption of lead(II) depends upon the surface adsorption only in the column test, where intraparticle and pore sorbed phenomenon are not so important with increasing concentration of adsorbate.

Effect of down flow rate : The effect of flow rate on lead(II) adsorption onto HTO columns (height : 3.7 cm, id : 0.7 cm) was determined with varying down flow rate (3.0, 2.0 and 1.0 ml/min) of a lead(II) solution (48.10 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) at an initial working pH 5.0. Breakthrough volume increased significantly with decreasing flow rate. The breakthrough capacities calculated for the said influent loading concentration were of 168.35 (± 4.81), 264.55 (± 9.45) and 360.75 (± 10.10) μmol , while column capacities were of 288.60 (± 7.01), 505.05 (± 8.50) and 649.35 (± 7.85) μmol respectively. The greater breakthrough and column capacities with decreasing flow rate (increasing contact) are due to the intraparticle transport and pore sorption of the sorbate ion with rapid surface mass transfer effect.

Effect of bed depth : The effect of contact time on lead(II) adsorption was also carried out with varying bed depth of HTO columns. Here, the columns depths used for laboratory investigation were of 1.3, 2.5 and 3.7 cm, respectively. The influent loading concentration used was 48.10 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ at pH 5.0, and down flow rate was of 3 ml/min. Treated volume of water with lead(II) below permissible level were of 0.35 (± 0.01), 1.80 (± 0.01) and 3.5 (± 0.15) L. The respective break-through capacities (16.84 (± 0.48), 86.58 (± 5.29) and 168.35 (± 7.22) μmol and column capacities (40.89 (± 3.11), 216.45 (± 4.25) and 360.75 (± 4.90) μmol) showed that the efficiency of HTO columns increased with increasing bed depth. The striking feature was the increase of column adsorption efficiency somewhat more than the proportionate amount. This is due to the greater possibility of intra-particle and pore diffusion of adsorbate species with increasing contact time.

Column application to lead(II)-contaminated industrial waste water : The column method was applied to the lead(II)-contaminated wastewater which was collected from the factory of Exide India Limited (EIL) for battery manufacturing, Shyamnagar, North 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India. This factory is in the eastern bank of the Hoogly River. The sample was collected and analysed (Table 3). Results showed that lead concentration (2.94 mg/L i.e. 14.13 $\mu\text{mol/L}$)

Table 3. Parameters of industrial waste water

Parameter	Before treatment	After treatment
pH	5.74 (± 0.02)	5.2 (± 0.01)
COD	170.00 (± 10)	145.00 (± 11)
DO	4.40 (± 0.21)	4.00 (± 0.25)
Lead	2.94 (± 0.03)	0.05 (± 0.01)
Nickel	BDL	BDL
Copper	0.09 (± 0.01)	BDL
Cadmium	BDL	BDL
Zinc	0.11 (± 0.02)	BDL
Nitrate	3.18 (± 0.012)	2.87 (± 0.15)
Chloride	15.00 (± 1.5)	15.00 (± 0.80)
Sulphate	86.47 (± 3.50)	78.32 (± 2.91)
Phosphate	2.65 (± 0.45)	2.58 (± 0.01)
Total hardness	330.00 (± 15)	320.00 (± 12)
Alkalinity	190.00 (± 11)	175.00 (± 9)
TDS	1014.00 (± 20)	978.00 (± 18)
TSS	24.00 (± 0.55)	18.00 (± 0.58)

All parameters are measured in mg/L except pH.
BDL : Below detectable limit.

L) with chemical oxygen demand (COD) and total dissolved solids (TDS) was much higher than their permissible level.

Here a column (id : 0.7 cm) packed with HTO (height : 3.7 cm) was used. The waste effluent was added at the top of the column and allowed to flow downwards at 1.0 ml/min. The treated water was collected and analysed. Results showed (Table 3) that the specified column generates 22.6 L of treated water with lead(II) concentration 0.2404 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (50 ppb). The HTO column reduces not only lead(II), but also reduces copper and zinc well below their contamination level indicating that this adsorbent material can also be used for copper and zinc contaminated waste water treatment.

Materials and methods :

Lead nitrate (G.R., E. Merck) was used for the preparation of stock solution (9.6154 mM), 1.0 ml nitric acid (A.R., B.D.H.) was added to prevent hydrolysis of the solution. For pH adjustment through out the experiment, 1.0 M solutions of aforesaid nitric acid and/or sodium hydroxide (Reagent grade, B.D.H.) was used as necessary. Lead solution was standardized by EDTA titration as usual. Titanium tetrachloride (L.R., E. Merck) was used for adsorbent synthesis. Reagent grade ammonium hydroxide was used as necessary.

Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Model-100) and Elico pH meter (Model- LI-127) were used

for trace lead(II) and pH determinations, respectively.

Synthesis of adsorbent : Titanium tetrachloride (0.455 mol) was added into a mechanically agitated 6.0L of deionized water and then, 0.5 M NH₄OH solution was added slowly to the hydrolyzed titanium hydroxide emulsion till the pH reached to 4.0. Precipitated hydroxide was allowed to age for ten days. Decanting supernat liquid, washed with water till acid free, and dried at 100°. Dried product was treated with water and used for the experiments.

Adsorption procedure :

Batch operation :

50 ml aliquot of lead(II) solutions (14.43 to 48.10 µM/L) was taken with ~0.1 g of HTO into a 100 ml clean polythene containers, and agitated (120 to 130 rpm) mechanically for an hour excepting the determination of equilibrium time experiments for maximum adsorption and kinetics. After agitations, all samples solutions were filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter, and the filtrate was analyzed for lead(II). The blank tests under the same conditions were also performed. This procedure was used for all adsorption experiments for evaluating pH influence, contact time for kinetics and isotherms, and the effect of other ions. The amount adsorbed was calculated by the difference of the initial and residual amount of lead(II) in solutions divided by the weight (in g) of adsorbent used. All batch experiments were conducted at room temperature, 30 (±3)°C and repeated thrice.

Desorption study :

Regeneration of lead(II)-rich HTO (lead content : 22.7 µmol/g) was tested by batch experiment at 30 (±3) °C. Here, 100 ml 0.01 M solution of HCl, HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ was added per gram of lead(II)-adsorbed HTO separately and agitated (agitation speed : 120–130 rpm) for an hour. Thereafter, the concentration of best possible desorbing agent(s) was (or were) varied with varying contact time for optimization of the method.

Recovery of lead(II) :

Experimental solution was concentrated to one third of its volume, neutralised and lead was precipitated with 5% K₂Cr₂O₇ solution after acidification with acetic acid, fil-

tered and dried at 120°. The excess dichromate in filtrate was reduced to chromium(III) with NaHSO₃ before disposal.

The effect on influent concentration of lead(II) was studied by loading 14.43, 24.05 and 48.10 µM/L solutions onto a fixed adsorbent bed (height : 3.7 cm) and a down flow rate (1.0 ml/min). The bed depth influence was determined by using 1.3, 2.5, and 3.7 cm of HTO packed columns with a fixed influent adsorbate concentration (48.10 µM/L) and down flow rate (3 ml/min), respectively. The influence of contact time on the sorption of the sorbate was carried out with varying down flow rate (1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 ml/min) using a fixed bed (3.7 cm) depth and influent concentration (48.10 µM/L).

Conclusions :

The optimum pH range for lead(II) sorption is 5.0 to 6.0 and the equilibrium contact time for the sorption process is only an hour. Determined maximum sorption capacity from 0.481 mM solution is 0.206 (±0.009) µmol lead(II)/g of adsorbent. Lead(II) sorption onto HTO takes place by both cation-exchange and van der Waals interaction phenomena. The adsorption kinetics for lead(II) at pH 5.0 has been well described by both Power function and Simple Elovich equations. Equilibrium lead(II) sorption data indicate the applicability of HTO for trace elimination from contaminated water. The systematic lab-bench column adsorption data show the possibility of technical scale applicability of HTO packed bed for lead(II) contaminated water treatment.

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